

The Present Day Relevance of the Life and Work of Acharya P. C. Ray. Part-I† Phytochemicals in New Frontiers. Part-II†

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THE PRESENT DAY RELEVANCE OF THE LIFE AND WORK OF ACHARYA P. C. RAY

I feel greatly honoured for being elected by the Indian Chemical Society to deliver the Acharya P. C. Ray Memorial Lecture for 1988. I am grateful to the Society for the honour done to me. As per stipulation of the award, some aspects of the life and work of Acharya is also to be covered in the lecture. So, I wish to present the lecture in two parts.

According to Rabindranath Tagore¹, a greatman like a great river rejuvenates the spiritual and the intellectual life of people around him initiating newer movements which spread over his time and sometimes country. The canvas of the activities of Acharya Ray was vast as such he participated in various movements. Greatmen of his time gave affectionate names to him in appreciation of his activities in different areas^{2,3}.

On the background of the great appreciation by the eminent personalities, I feel extremely diffident to speak anything on the life and work of Acharya Ray. Still I consider myself fortunate to dwell on some aspects of his activities for a few minutes to pay homage to Acharya Ray at a historic place wherefrom a great philosopher and an intellectual of ages, Lord Buddha initiated spreading his gospel.

P. C. Ray was born in the year 1861, the year in which Rabindranath Tagore, Motilal Nehru, Brahmabandhab Upadhyaya and Nilratan Sarkar were born. Incidentally, the years 1858-1872, record the birth of a galaxy of great Indian personalities³ who contributed to the development of modern India leading to its independence.

All these intellectuals were influenced by the liberal movement initiated by Raja Ram Mohun Roy in the second decade of the Nineteenth century which culminated into various social reforms, the establishment of English education and three Universities in India in 1857, the year of Sepoy mutiny. These sociocultural backgrounds perhaps provided them a lure for establishing a new Indian identity in their respective fields. This goal was probably the basis

of the driving power for their creativity, idomitable courage and working programmes.

P. C. Ray came from a well-to-do intellectual Bengali family. He was influenced by his father and Brahmananda Keshab Chandra for developing a rational and liberal outlook of life. In his professional career he was influenced by Sir Alexander Pedler of Presidency College, Calcutta, to take up chemistry which is evident from his own tribute to Sir Alexander⁴ :

'Pedler's neat manipulation, experimental skill and persuasive lectures contributed not a little to the popularity of the subject and it is from him that the present speaker who had the good fortune to sit at the feet for close upon four years, acquired a taste for the cultivation of chemistry'.

After obtaining D.Sc. degree of Edinburgh University, he joined Presidency College as a teacher in chemistry in 1889. In 1895, Ray developed a chemical laboratory which became the cradle of modern Indian chemical research. There he also faced a strong discriminatory attitude of the Government between the Indian members of educational service and their British counterparts⁴. The strong sense of Indian nationalism in him prompted him to join the first 'Indian Science Movement' already initiated by Mahendra Lal Sarkar, J. C. Bose and Asutosh Mookerjee⁵. In 1896, he published his paper on mercurous nitrite in the *Journal of Asiatic Society*⁶ which immediately attracted the attention of the *Journal Nature*. In one of its issues in 1896 *Nature* commented⁷

'The Journal of Asiatic Society can scarcely be said to have a place in our libraries. The current number contains a paper by P. C. Ray of Presidency College. Calcutta on mercurous nitrite is worthy of note'.

This act of P. C. Ray nearly a century ago has a strong relevance today when the Indian science journals have been cited to have poor citation index^{8,9}. How can the journals record a good citation index if they are starved of the good papers

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produced in India with Indian resources and published outside India. For the improvement of the situation it is imperative that they should be published in India. Even though it may mean some amount of personal sacrifice on the part of the contributors it will benefit the nation in the long run. It may be cited that Raman published his paper on Raman effect in 1928 in *Nature* as well as in the journal published from Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta¹⁰. This¹⁰ gave him the priority of his findings. M. N. Saha published one of his papers relating to thermal ionisation in 1924 in our Society's journal¹¹.

Acharya Ray was alive to the economic improvement of the country through industries. He was founder of various industries. The Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works established in 1901, his first experiment in initiating industry in the country, was a commercial success. He believed in the development of the indigenous innovative processes for the continuous growth of industrial houses. For this he wished that some funds out of company's profit should be set apart for the development of innovative processes. In 1939, he had some differences with the management of the company on this issue and he resigned as the Director of the Company². The concept of the development through indigenous innovative processes could be considered as the forerunner of the in-house R & D as defined in the technology policy statement of the Government of India in 1983. The rigorous improvement of the research and development programmes is one of the ways to improve the economy and the employment potential of the scientists of the country. Today with the availability of foreign collaborations, foreign aid and imported technology, the input of indigenous innovative processes as compared to our requirements have become less necessary. So, the development of individual and national initiatives in innovations and the consequential development of human resources are slowly becoming less available as compared to our requirements for adequately facing the world competition. The situation calls for immediate modification to organise human and natural resources to make some progress in wiping out our external debts which has grown¹² from 20.65 billion dollars in 1980 to 62.50 billion in 1989.

Acharya Ray had a firm conviction in the freedom of thought and action for the good of the country. This is clearly reflected in his message to Basanti Debi in the wake of the non-cooperation movement and the arrest of Deshbandhu Chitta Ranjan Das that 'Science can wait but not Swaraj'. The firm conviction found expression also in his activities in the University of Calcutta which helped Asutosh Mookerjee¹³ to build firmly the post-graduate system of education and to lay the foundation of modern edifice of science and technology in India through University system of education. It is the University system of education through which appropriate manpower for the various walks of life are produced. The Universities being situated in

different parts of the country, they can look into the educational and technological needs of the country in various parts as they have larger access to young scientists at different regions. The healthy development of these regions are necessary as this will help the less developed areas to grow up. Such development will restrict the future problems arising from unbalanced developments from region to region.

P. C. Ray had a deep sense of belonging to the common masses and readily stood by them in their distress even at a high stake. His initiative and successful management of relief operations in floods and famine in different parts of Bengal in the face of Government inaction are some of the examples of his deep feelings. His management of Damodar flood in 1922 which was acclaimed by the English Press, shows the magnitude of task he ventured to undertake. This will be apparent from the report of G. T. Gwyn in the *Manchester Guardian*² (November 11, 1922), a small part of which is quoted below :

'The Government took slow action or no action at all, whatever the Government gave, it gave reluctantly under public pressure.

'In these circumstances a Professor of Chemistry, Sir P. C. Ray, stepped forward and called upon his countrymen to make good the Government's omission. His call was answered with enthusiasm.

'The enthusiasm of the response to Sir P. C. Ray's appeal was due partly to Bengali's national desire to score off the foreign Government, partly to genuine public sympathy with sufferers and very largely to Sir P. C. Ray's remarkable personality and position. He is a very strong nationalist and a very strong critic of the Government. He is also a real organiser and real teacher'.

In the light of the declaration of the present decade as the decade of natural disaster reduction by UNESCO and wide-spread aid pouring from various international, national and non-Government organisations for their management, P. C. Ray's bold endeavours calls for newer assessment. Besides the great organising ability of Acharya Ray, these endeavours reflect his great anxiety to stand by the men in distress even in problems which may be considered apparently beyond the capacity of individual management. He attained success in these tasks with unbelievable fortitude. The spirit underlying these activities should give impetus to younger scientists and social workers.

During the relief work of the Damodar flood in 1922 he came in close contact with the common people of the villages. From the survey of their economic conditions he concluded that they could increase their daily income by one anna (seven paise) taking recourse to spinning. According his calculations, if such spinning of *Charka* could be undertaken by people at the grass-root level throughout India, it would save India Rs. 182 crores of foreign exchange a year in those days. In the C. R. Das Memorial Meeting held at Calcutta in 1925, he was found spinning in presence of Mahatma Gandhi. It is from the consideration of the economic welfare of the masses he was an ardent advocate of *Charka* and *Khadi*. In the areas of organisation of science

societies he worked with people who gave adequate help and feed-back for his fruitful endeavours like his followers in other fields.

P. C. Ray was a selfless man who gave about 90% of his earnings for noble causes, and for the benefit of the poor and the distressed. The gift of the total earning from 1922 to 1935 as the Palit Professor of Calcutta University may be cited as an example¹⁴. The money was utilised for the construction of a part of the second floor in the south wing of the Science College building at 92, A. P. C. Road, Calcutta, in a portion of which the Indian Chemical Society is housed.

The leadership given by P. C. Ray in various movements could be considered to be an expression of collective aspiration of the people in general, particularly the people around him. In this respect he stands out unique amongst the initiators of the first 'Indian Science Movement'. He passed away in 1944 and did not live to see the expanded success of the movement for which he and his contemporaries strove. Self-complacency and self-centeredness are few of the backlashes of the success of most of the movements. These factors may cause the distraction of the goal of 'Science Movements' and may also weaken the edifice of science and technology, the foundation of which has been laid down by its initiators with great dedication and foresight. The onus lies with the leadership of science today to be constantly vigilant over these backlashes for continuous progress in science and technology in the country to lead the movements in the right direction.

P. C. Ray is a symbol of dedicated struggle for freedom, scientific enquiry and elimination of

poverty of the common Indian. The legendary 'Father of Indian Chemical Sciences'³ is more relevant today when the country is passing through economic crisis and erosion of moral values. He inspires all generations in fruitful and challenging endeavours for the good of the people.

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PHYTOCHEMICALS IN NEW FRONTIERS

THE advancement of our knowledge in phytochemicals of terrestrial origin is 'primarily due to the initiative of the European commercial interest in the nineteenth century for the better utilisation of the plant resources of the world. This pragmatic approach paid the world a good dividend as such by 1960, nearly 6000 discrete chemical compounds of small molecular dimensions were known^{1,2}. Some of these compounds are important from biological, therapeutic and other commercial considerations. But the majority of the compounds was considered as metabolic wastes.

With the understanding of the implications of phytochemicals in phylogenic relatedness of species based on Darwinian³ and Mendelian⁴ concepts, the rationale of the orderly distribution of the structurally related phytochemicals in biologically related species began to be clarified⁵. But the molecular basis of micromolecular taxonomy (chemical taxonomy) has been established only after the discovery of DNA as the genetic material which has been shown to regulate morphogenesis and enzyme-

mediated synthesis of small molecules in species. Since then there has been wider interest in the area of micromolecular taxonomy⁶. But various questions like the object of the synthesis of micromolecules in species since the advent of green plants and their biochemical or ecological functions remained unanswered.

Two important concepts in 1959 and afterwards, directed the dynamics of our thinking in new frontiers of phytochemistry. In 1959, Fraenkel⁷ proposed that all the molecules produced by a species have some biochemical function or other. This spoke of the wider role of the small molecules in biology, specially of those hitherto considered waste products of metabolism. This concept was the turning point of investigations on the various biochemical and ecological functions of phytochemicals. In 1966, Erlich and Raven⁸ came forward with concept of the angiosperm shielding wherein it was conceived that the small molecules provide a biochemical shield under the protection of which angiosperms have survived through ages and have become diverse

These concepts led to immediate thinking that we are dependent on small molecules for our existence as angiosperms and biomolecules of small molecular dimensions provide various needs for the existence of animal species. In short, we are dependent upon some macromolecules for the genesis of the life processes while, on some small molecules derived through some of them, for its maintainance and functioning.

The small molecules which act as signals in various interactions of plant species around its environment are important from ecological considerations. Closely at the heels of these concepts came the discovery of *Salvia* phenomenon⁹ in 1966. It was shown that simple terpenes like cineole and camphor after degradation by soil microflora around *Salvia leucophylla* inhibited the growth of plants around it. From this time onwards there has been sizeable progress of our understanding on phytochemical ecology⁹, allelopathy¹⁰ and allelochemic substances. Allelochemic substances are very important as they influence the dominance, productivity, succession and vegetation dynamics. From the consideration of agrarian economy, the knowledge about allelochemic substances provides a new approach to agro-ecosystem management.

In 150 years of phytochemical investigations in India one major thrust has been based primarily on the pragmatic approach¹¹. In this respect Ayurvedic and other indigenous systems of medicine together with the commercial uses of the plants have provided important guiding information¹². This paid the nation a good dividend as will be evident from some data cited here (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PRAGMATIC APPROACH (SOME RELEVANT DATA)

Export of plant and plant products in 1982	Worth nearly 200 million US dollars ^a
Total essential oil production in 1982	11256 tonne ^a
Total production of turpentine oil in 1982	9000 tonne ^a
Approximate production of plant resin per year	35000 tonne ^a
Number of chemical compounds from Indian plants used as drugs	Over 50
Internal use of plant extracts and tinctures as drugs	Extensive uses in modern and indigenous systems affecting national economy and health

^aRef. 13

Investigations relating to micromolecular taxonomy (then known as chemical taxonomy) in India were carried out first by R. G. Chatterjee¹⁴ of Calcutta Presidency College during 1946–56. Since then investigations in this area continued specially in the laboratory of 'Comparative Phytochemistry' at Bose Institute. The investigations on the biochemical function of phytochemicals have been carried out in several laboratories during the last two decades in India. These approaches provide

an organic chemist a way of understanding the role of phytochemicals in their totality where isolation, structure determination and synthesis are means to an end. The first discussions on 'Micromolecular Ecology'¹⁵ in India was held in a National Symposium on Micromolecular Ecology at Bose Institute, Calcutta, in 1986.

Since 1960, our attention was drawn to the segregation of the order Rutales from Geranials by Hutchinson¹⁶ in his lignosae. In 1964, the present worker¹⁷ drew attention to the fact that aromatics, aromatics with mevalonate fragments and nor-terpenoids of limonin group are characteristic compounds for the species belonging to the above group. It was further pointed out by the present speaker that the limonoids reflect the closeness of the families Rutaceae, Meliaceae and Simaroubaceae. The alkaloids of anthranilic acid origin are characteristic for the family Rutaceae. Almost simultaneously, Dreyer¹⁸ pointed out in 1964 the occurrence of limonoids in taxonomically related Rutaceae, Meliaceae and Simaroubaceae. Price¹⁹ on the other hand showed in 1963 that anthranilic acid derived alkaloids are characteristic for the family Rutaceae. Subsequent worldwide interest in the area has been reflected in the comprehensive discussions on the 'Chemistry and Chemical Taxonomy on the order Rutales'²⁰ in 1983 wherein the aforementioned ideas find confirmation.

We reported from *Clausena heptaphylla* the first pentanortriterpenoid of limonin group²¹, clausenolide (1) in which one carbon in ring-A from C₂₆-skeleton of limonin has been lost. The structure

was established from its physical data, reactions and X-ray crystallographic data (Fig. 1). Subsequent to our investigations several members with this pentanortriterpenoid skeletal unit including ichangensin have been isolated and characterised from the members of the family Rutaceae²². The genesis of the modified ring-A can be visualised as proceeding by deacetyl nomilnic acid (2) and β -keto acid (3) followed by decarboxylation to a ketone and ring closure to a hemiacetyl system. Alternatively, the oxidation of deacetyl nomilnic acid (2) or isobacunic acid (4) would yield the same result. From the stem bark of *Murraya koenigii* Spreng,

Fig. 1. Stereoscopic view of the molecular structure of Clausenolide.

we have isolated a norsteroid named koenolide^{23a} (5). The structure has been arrived at from its physical data and some reactions. It was the C₂₈-residue of the steroidal side-chain modified to a six-membered ring system similar to those in bourjotinolones (6), physalin (7) and astrahyrol (8) recently reported from Basidiomycetes^{23b}.

Our interest in *Swetenia mahagoni* (Fam. Meliaceae) for protolimonoids resulted in the isolation of cyclomahogenol²⁴ (9), the structure of which has been determined from its reaction, physical data and the conversion of diketocyclomahogenol (10) to 24-methylcycloartane (11) and 24-methylene cycloartane (12). Grandifolione (13) has been cited as an intermediate in the biosynthetic sequence of the conversion of ring-D to ring-D-lactone. In plants elaborating furanolactones, tetracyclic triterpenes with 16-hydroxyl groups were unknown previous to our work. The oxygenation at 16-position may be an expression of an intermediate in an alternative biosynthetic pathway for the conversion of ring-D to ring-D-lactone.

The ozonisation²⁵ of diketocyclomahogenol probably gave 7,24-dioxo compound similar ozonisation product of 24-methylene cyclo

acetate when 7,24-dioxo compound (14) was obtained. With the understanding of the participation of vinologous ozone in various model enzymatic hydroxylations¹⁵, it may be suggested that the gene-

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10 ; $R_1=R_2=(=O)$, $R_3=CH_3$, $R_4=H$
14 ; $R_1=OH$, $R_2=H$, $R_3=CH_3$, $R_4=H$

Ozonisation product of **10** ; $R_1=R_2=R_3=(=O)$, $R_4=OH$
 Ozonisation product of **14** ; $R_1=OH$, $R_2=H$, $R_3=R_4=(=O)$

ration of the double bond at 7,8-position may arise alternatively from prior hydroxylation of some triterpene system and subsequent dehydration.

In addition to these we have reported 7-deacetyl-7-oxogedunin^{26a}, 6-hydroxymethyl angolensate^{26b}, melianone^{26c}, mahogendiol^{26d} (**15**) and swemanol^{26e} (**16**) from *S. mahagoni*. The structures of **15** and **16** have been assigned from their physical data and some reactions.

15

16

17A

18 ; $R_1=R_2=CH_3$
19 ; $R_1=H$, $R_2=CH_3$

The precedence of allylic cleavage of the steroid like **17** leading to the formation of **17A** during mass spectral fragmentation²⁷, the report of cycloweietenol²⁸ (**18**) and nor-cyclowietenol²⁹ (**19**) by Anjaneyulu *et al.* from *Swietenia mahagoni* and the recent biosynthetic demonstration on the cyclisation of hexapolyprenyl system in *Tetrahymena pyriformis*³⁰ giving rise to tricyclic triterpene system with a chain of C_{11} -units (**20**) provide a strong credence to structure of mahogendiol with a straight chain of C_{11} -unit. Interestingly, the genus *Swietenia* shows an array of a large number of triterpenoids starting from C_{31} -unit like cyclomahogenol to C_{26} triterpenoids at different oxidation levels ending in bicyclononanolides, specifically demonstrating various types of transformations of a tetracyclic triterpene to tetranor species taking place in a particular genus.

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Today over 400 structurally different limonoids³¹⁻³³ of different families reported from the families Rutaceae, Meliaceae, Simaroubaceae and Cnorraceae add further to the credence of generalisation made by the present speaker in 1964, with respect to the occurrence of limonoids in taxonomically related plants.

Previously³⁴ degraded triterpenoids like dammaronic acid (**21**) and nyctanthic acid (**22**) have been reported from families higher up in evolution like Bursaraceae and Nyctanthaceae. We were interested to look for degraded triterpenes in the family Leguminosae which is lower down in evolution and is versatile in giving expression to various types of phytochemicals³⁵. Though no degraded triterpene like limonin has been reported from the family, hycanogenin³⁵ showing the presence of a lactone system representing a degradation of C_8 -sidechain of tetracyclic triterpene, has been reported from the family. On the basis of this precedence, we examined the stem bark *Saraca indica* wherefrom first hexnortriterpenoid sardicone (**23**) has been isola-

Chart 1. Some biogenetically related triterpenoids of the genus *Swietenia*.

ted. The position of the hydroxyl at 15- and the double bond at 7,8-position has been corroborated

from ^1H nmr data of the acetate of sardicone wherein the signal for the proton at 7-position has been found to be deshielded and shifted to δ 7.10 from 5.28 showing the presence of the hydroxyl at C-15. The elimination of the side-chain at the allylic position during mass spectral fragmentation also support the assignment of the double bond at 7,8-position. From this, it is conceivable that the

degraded triterpenoids may also be reported from other families lower down in evolution. Newer data may provide further information to have newer micromolecular taxonomic interrelationship.

The family Rutaceae is abundant with coumarins carrying structural fragments derived MVA unit^{37a,b}. The genus *Murraya*^{37c} has been examined for its coumarinic constituents wherefrom more than forty coumarins with such structural features have been isolated. These include simple coumarins with a straight chain of C_5 or C_{10} units. We reported structures of mexoticin³⁸ (24) and mexolide³⁹ (25) from *M. exotica*. Dimeric coumarins like thamnusin⁴⁰ (26) have been isolated from *Thamnosia montana*, *Zanthoxylum suberosum*⁴¹, *Phebalium dentatum*⁴² and *Toddalia aculeata*⁴³ of the family Rutaceae. The cyclohexene system in thamnusin was suggested by Kutney to arise from a hypothetical diene system like 26A by 1,4-cycloaddition. Mexoticin on dehydration with P_2O_5 in boiling xylene yielded mexolide as one of the products probably due to the generation of the diene (24A) and its 2,4-cycloaddition product mexolide. This partial biogenetic type synthesis of mexolide provides further evidence to the biogenetic ideas put forward by Kutney. This has also been supported by the recent isolation of exolide (27) from *M. exotica*.

We reported from *Mesua ferrea*^{44,45}, a member of the family Guttiferae, mesuol (**29**) and mesuagin (**30**) two 4-phenylcoumarins. The production of 4-phenylcoumarins is a speciality of the family. The structure of mesuol was determined from its physical data, degradation studies and its conversion to isomesuol (**31**) by treatment with alkali. The total synthesis of mesuagin (**30**)⁴⁶ from **28**, regiospecific synthesis of angular isomesuagin (**32**)⁴⁷ and the conversion of mesuol to isomesuol in good yield by us contrary to the views of Djerassi *et al.*⁴⁸ and Crombie *et al.*⁴⁹, together with Bala and Seshadri's⁵⁰ synthesis of mesuagin from mesuol, confirm the structures of mesuol, mesuagin and isomesuol. Seshadri in 1957, suggested that 4-phenylcoumarins are formed from a phenolic unit and a C₆-C₃ unit. This idea was supported from biosynthetic studies of calophyllolide

by Kunes and Polonosky⁵¹. Mukherjee *et al.*⁵² suggested that in the neoflavonoid biosynthesis, 4-phenylcoumarins occupy a key position while 4-phenylcoumarins are formed by *o*-acylation of reactive phenol with cinnamoyl coenzyme followed by cyclisation of cinnamic ester. The thermal trans-

formation^{53a} of phenyl cinnamate yielded 4-phenylcoumarin, *trans*-stilbene and 3-cinnamoylcinnamate while the methanolic solution of phenyl cinnamate in presence of iodine after photolysis^{53b} with low pressure mercury vapour lamp (16 W) in nitrogen atmosphere gave 4-phenylcoumarin in low yield. These results provide a laboratory analogy for the biogenetic concept advanced by Mukherjee *et al.* The production of *trans*-stilbene opens out the thinking that phenyl cinnamate may also serve as the precursor of compounds arising from stilbene in plants i.e. phenanthrenes and stilbenes.

The taxonomic approach has been most fruitful in the area carbazole alkaloids. We were looking for anthranilic acid derived alkaloids from members of Rutaceae when murrayanine, the first member of carbazole alkaloids, was isolated from *Murraya koenigii* Spreng. in 1962. Murrayanine⁵⁴ was formulated as 1-methoxy-3-formylcarbazole (Chart 2). Since then various types of monomeric

alkaloids were isolated by us from taxonomically related genera *Murraya*, *Clausena* and *Glycosmis*.

The anthranilate origin of these alkaloids, proposed by the present worker was also supported by

Furukawa after isolation of murrayaline (34). Kapil⁵⁶ suggested that 3-methylcarbazole (35) is the progenitor of carbazoles of higher plants. This was supported by the isolation of 3-methyl carbazole from *Clausena heptaphylla* by us^{54b}. In order to

36

37

37A

gain an insight into the genesis of 2-hydroxy-3-methylcarbazole (36) progenitor of a large number of carbazole alkaloids, we undertook biomimetic hydroxylation of 3-methylcarbazole using Udenfriend reaction, a prototype of monooxygenase and mixed function oxidase reactions when 2-hydroxy-3-methylcarbazole was obtained as a major product. In addition, we obtained a dimeric product (37) from which we predicted that dimeric carbazole alkaloids may occur in nature^{54c, 55a}. The prediction has been proved to be correct due to isolation of the first dimeric carbazole alkaloid murrayaline (37A) from *Murraya euchrestifolia*. During the three decades from 1962 there has been world wide interest in carbazole alkaloids. More than hundred monomeric and dimeric alkaloids are known which have been isolated from various sources primarily from taxonomically related higher plants. The alkaloids have also been isolated from bacterial and marine sources as well as from mammalian sources. New methods of synthesis of the tetra-, penta- and hexacyclic systems have been reported^{54b, 56-58}.

The closeness of the families Rutaceae, Meliaceae and Simaroubaceae is reflected in limonoids of these families. The steroid alkaloids and cardiac aglycones of Apocynaceae showing the similarity of some biochemical reactions³⁴ in Apocynaceae with Rutaceae, suggests their closeness. Some alkaloids of Rutaceae arising out of combined mevalonate and anthranilate pathway, and the indole alkaloids derived from mixed pathway of indoles and mevalonates, characteristic of the families Loganiaceae,

Apocynaceae, Rubiaceae complex, reflect the closeness of these families with Rutaceae^{6a, 17a}.

Two quinoxaline alkaloids glomerine (38) and homoglomerine (39) secreted by the American millipedes *Glomeria marginata* have been shown to protect the millipedes from their predators. The quinoxaline alkaloids⁵⁹ are also abundant in the family Rutaceae. So, on taxonomic and ecological considerations we were interested with these alkaloids. From the flower heads of *Glycosmis pentaphylla* we isolated glycopyimine (40) and its enol-ether glycopyimoline (41). Glycopyimine was synthesised from phenylacetanilide (41A) and urethane under reflux condition in presence of P₂O₅. It has been shown⁶⁰ that -CONH₂ group from urethane attacks the *ortho*-position of the anilide nitrogen giving (41B) and undergoes ring closure involving the amide nitrogen with carbon of the anilide carbonyl, generating a double bond between 2,3-position of the quinoxalin-1,4-one. This has been clearly demonstrated with synthesis of arborine (42) by the above method.

(41A)

(43)

(40)

Pakrashi and Bhattacharyya* repeated the synthesis of glycopyimine and ended with glycosmicine (43). The synthesis of arborine, glycopyimine and glycosmicine by the above method provides a chemical proof in addition to already known spectroscopic evidences for the stability of double bond at 1,2-position rather than between 3,4-position in 1,4-quinoxalinones without any substitution at 1-position. It establishes that glycopyimine is the intermediate in the synthesis of glycosmicine by the above method.

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The aminocarbonylation reaction reported by Chakraborty *et al.*⁶⁰ could be considered a convenient modification of Gatterman's amidation reaction and a prototype of biological carbamoylation reaction involved in urea cycle as well as in the synthesis of dihydroorotic acid (44), a key intermediate for pyrimidine nucleotide synthesis with carbamyl phosphate through enzyme mediation⁶¹.

TABLE 2—GROWTH INHIBITORY PROPERTY OF SOME POLYCYCLIC COMPOUNDS*

Compd.	MIC (ppm)	
	Light	Dark
(A) Arylbenzenes		
57; R ₂ =R ₃ =CH ₃ , R ₁ =R ₄ =H	1	1
58; R ₁ =R ₃ =CH ₃ , R ₂ =R ₄ =H	1	1
59; R ₂ =R ₄ =CH ₃ , R ₁ =R ₃ =H	1	1
(B) Arylnaphthalenes		
60; R ₂ =R ₃ =CH ₃ , R ₁ =R ₄ =H	1	1
61; R ₁ =R ₂ =CH ₃ , R ₃ =R ₄ =H	1	1
62; R ₂ =R ₄ =CH ₃ , R ₁ =R ₃ =H	1	1
63; R ₁ =R ₂ =CH ₃ , R ₃ =H	5	5
64; R ₁ =R ₂ =CH ₃ , R ₃ =H	1	1
(C) 7,12-Diphenylbenz(K)fluorathenes		
65; R ₁ =R ₂ =CH ₃ , R ₃ =H	0.5	0.5
66; R ₂ =R ₃ =CH ₃ , R ₁ =H	5	5
67; R ₁ =R ₃ =CH ₃ , R ₂ =H	0.5	0.5
68; R ₃ =CH ₃ , R ₁ =R ₂ =H	1	1
(D) 7,14-Disubstituted-acenaphtho(1,2-K)fluorathenes		
69; R ₁ =R ₂ =C ₄ H ₉	1	1
70; R ₁ =R ₂ =C ₈ H ₇	5	5
71; R ₁ =R ₂ =C ₂ H ₅	1	10

*Ref. 68

Ecdysones which are ecologically important are abundant in the genus, *Amaranthaceae*. We were interested from taxonomic considerations to find out ecdysone from *Amaranthus viridis*⁶⁹ which is commonly used as a common vegetable in our country.

A steroid, amasterol having a homoannular diene system in the ring-B was isolated, which was assigned the structure 72 from its physical properties and reactions.

The conversion of 7-dehydrocholesterol (73) to 5 β -cholest-en-3 β -ol (74) takes place in microorganisms. The steroid is present in the gut of certain insects and may serve as precursor of ecdysones in such cases. Therefore, $\Delta^{6,7}$ -diene may serve as a precursor of ecdysones. The presence of amasterol ($\Delta^{6,7}$ -diene), spinosterol (Δ^7 -steroid) in *Amaranthus viridis* and ecdysones in *Amaranthaceae* is suggestive of such a biosynthetic series.

Amasterol and its derivatives inhibit seed germination and growth of seedlings. Amasterol strongly inhibits the growth of *Helminthosporium oryzae*, a pathogenic fungi.

We also reported steroids glycosterol (75)⁷⁰ and dehydro- β -sitosterol (76)⁷¹ with ring-B homoannular diene system from *Glycosmis pentaphylla* and *Rauwolfia serpentina*. Glycosterol was identified with dihydroamasterol. Dehydro- β -sitosterol was however previously detected in a mixture by gc and mass spectral studies only, not isolated in pure state.

78

79

Our interest in the various biological properties of the phytochemicals in relation to ecology led to the discovery of antifeedant properties of some compounds and some newer antifeedants from crop plants. Xanthindiol has been isolated from the leaves of *Tricoxanthes dioica*⁷² whose structure has been arrived at from the physical and spectral properties as 77. It has been found to have antifeedant action against *Dicrisia obliqua* at a concentration of 6.25 ppm, while psoralen (78) and isopsoralen (79) have been shown to be active at a concentration of 6.25 and 12.25 respectively.

80

The oils derived from some Umbelliferous and other spices were found to have contact toxicity⁷³. So, we were interested to isolate a bioactive substance from *Coriandrum sativum* wherefrom we got a steroid coriandiol (80)^{83b}. We have also examined the growth inhibitory activities of various coumarins^{28d}. Some of them have been found to have inhibitory activities on seed germination as well as on the root and shoot growth. The compounds have also been reported by us to have antibiotic action against various microorganisms; some of which are plant pathogens. Incidentally none have inhibitory action against *Azotobacter* sp. or *Rhizobium* sp. Exolide (27) has however been found to accelerate the growth of *Rhizobium* sp. at concentration of 1 ppm.

From the work carried out by us and from reports in literature, it is conceivable that biologically related plants produce ecologically important compounds of similar structure, thus tying up micromolecular ecology and micromolecular taxonomy. It lends further to the understanding that ecological factors mediated by micromolecules are dependent upon the genetic make up the plant species. It is a matter of common experience that majority of the constituents elaborated by plants have low biological toxicity. It might be an ecological requirement that the constituents should be deterrent to some herbivores or microorganisms but not always lethal to those species, so that they also survive in the ecosystem to play their role. Micromolecules are involved largely

in maintaining the functional aspects of species perhaps due to their higher mobility in cellular system.

In the Indian experience of phytochemistry since 1840, plants have been mainly utilised as sources for medicines and commercial chemicals. But today the phytochemicals have assumed much wider importance in agrarian economy and in the frontiers of biology. So, their vital role in shaping the agrobased life-style of common Indian can readily be visualised. Acharya Ray had a deep sense of belonging to the common people of the country. Perhaps the selection of a topic on the new frontiers of phytochemistry, having a strong relevance to the needs of common Indians, is justified for this memorial talk.

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